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D11.2 New interoperability specifications and policy recommendations

Work Package	WP11 - Ocean Science
Lead Author (Org)	Pier Luigi Buttigieg (AWI)
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Abbreviations and Acronyms

API	Application Programming Interface
CDIF	Cross-domain interoperability framework
CORDIS	Community Research and Development Information Service
DDI	Data Documentation Initiative
EBV	Essential Biodiversity Variable
EOV	Essential Ocean Variable
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EXIF	Exchangeable Image File
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FER	FAIR Enabling Resource
FIP	FAIR Implementation Profile
GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information Facility
GEO	Group on Earth Observations
GEO BON	Group on Earth Observations Biodiversity Observation Network
GOOS	Global Ocean Observing System
IIIF	International Image Interoperability Framework
IOC	Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission
IODE	International Oceanographic Data and Information Exchange
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
JSON(-LD)	JavaScript Object Notation (for Linked Data)
LOD	Linked Open Data

NODC	National Oceanographic Data Centre
NUTS	Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics
OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
OBIS	Ocean Biodiversity Information System
OBON	Ocean Biomolecular Observation Network
ODIN	Ocean Data and Information Network
ODIS	Ocean Data and Information System
ODIS-Arch	ODIS Architecture
ODIS-Cat	ODIS Catalogue of Sources
ODP	Ocean Data Portal
OIH	Ocean InfoHub
Omic BON	Omic Biodiversity Observation Network
OWL	Web Ontology Language
PID	Permanent Identifier
REST	REpresentational State Transfer
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RDF(S)	Resource Description Framework (Schema)
ROR	Research Organization Registry
SKOS	Simple Knowledge Organization System
UNDRR	United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction
UN Ocean Decade	United Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization
WOD	World Ocean Database
XML(S)	eXtensible Markup Language (Schema)

Executive Summary

Following closely from WorldFAIR Deliverable 11.1, this deliverable introduces a set of (meta)data interoperability specifications and recommendations for policies that would ensure their meaningful implementation and development within projects such as WorldFAIR and frameworks such as the Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF). This is a concrete step towards interoperable regional and global data spaces (in the terms technical and accurate sense) using domain and regionally neutral interoperability conventions. This is essential to power the emerging integrative, AI-augmented ecosystems such as digital twins, cloud-native solutions, and virtualisation engines.

Specifications developed in the central case study of Work Package (WP) 11 - the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission's Ocean Data and Information System (ODIS) - were screened for their appropriateness to the cross-domain goals of WorldFAIR, and are now ready for community review in the CDIF community development space. Collectively, these specifications are referred to as "CDIF Core" and include (meta)data exchange specifications for 44 entity types (including datasets and other creative works, projects, organisations, and software) that are now available for review by other domains. These specifications are already aligned to prevailing conventions and web architectural patterns used by millions of machines worldwide (based on exchange of JSON-LD/schema.org). As such, this deliverable reports on a concrete advancement of CDIF and anticipates demonstrations of cross-work-package digital exchanges. Should these exchanges be successful and the specifications be well-managed under CDIF, a pathway to come full circle and align ODIS to CDIF is also described.

Perhaps of more importance in the long-term, this deliverable also describes, at a technical level, how the CDIF Core specifications should be managed by WorldFAIR and external implementation groups to maintain coherence and alignment, while supporting discoverable innovation. It also describes 1) how to nest domain- or regionally-specific content into the domain-neutral CDIF Core; and 2) how co-developers may feed back into the CDIF Core specifications in a principled and fully traceable way.

Following this work, WP11 will - as described in Task 11.3 - leverage CDIF Core to pursue demonstrations of cross-domain interoperability with WorldFAIR partners (particularly in biodiversity, cultural heritage, and disaster risk reduction) and/or themes to confirm the viability of the approaches described in this report.

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1. Background

1.1. Context

This deliverable builds upon the background and recommendations in WorldFAIR Deliverable 11.1 (D11.1)¹, particularly in pursuing the Priority Areas outlined in Section 4 of that document. Recognising that the Ocean Science case study in itself is addressing a multi-domain challenge, D11.1 found that the interoperability solution used in the central case study of Work Package 11 (WP11) - the Ocean Data and Information System (ODIS) Architecture (ODIS-Arch) - was generalisable across domains. As such, and in pursuit of this deliverable, further work aimed to export the domain-neutral core of ODIS-Arch into the collaborative development environment supporting the Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF)², which is at the heart of WorldFAIR's mission. Please refer to D11.1 for introductory material on ODIS and WP11's approach to interfacing with other WorldFAIR WPs, based on an assessment of their FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs).

1.2. Strategic amendments

As work towards this deliverable was performed, amendments to the recommendations in D11.1 were made to both seize impactful opportunities and to ensure feasibility in pursuit of D11.3. These are summarised below.

The original description of the Task linked to this deliverable (Task 11.2; T11.2) is as follows:

Task 11.2: New interoperability specifications and policy recommendations

Based on the developments in Task 11.1, this task will enhance existing and create new ODIS-Arch specifications which have bearing on digital ecosystems beyond that of the ocean community. Based on these changes, a set of policy recommendations for the ODIS interoperability framework will be drafted for consideration by the IODE.

Following the completion of D11.1, and the progress of CDIF through efforts within and beyond WorldFAIR, the opportunity to enhance this delivery was taken. Instead of simply expanding ODIS-Arch within WP11, we have established a foundational, cross-domain set of (meta)data exchange specifications for co-development with the emerging CDIF community. This is in line with

¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7682399>

² <https://github.com/Cross-Domain-Interoperability-Framework>

the D11.1 recommendations in Section 4.3 (Phase 2 – Progressive co-implementation and strategic alignment)³:

Transfer the thematic interoperability conventions currently specified in ODIS-Arch⁴ into a domain-neutral space, under co-governance by a wider multidomain consortium. This will support more collaborative and community-driven evolution and synchrony with external standards.

This amendment allows the direct creation of new specifications (within established, cross-domain web architectural standards used by millions of web resources) by all case studies within WorldFAIR, as well as other CDIF stakeholders.

In relation to the perspectives for ODIS noted in D11.1 (Section 3.3), and their related Priority Areas (Section 4.1, particularly point 1 “Developing cross-domain interoperability along existing strategic and thematic priorities”), these amendments and growing familiarity with the other use cases have the following consequences:

1. **Disaster Risk Reduction (WP12):** The United Nations Disaster Risk Reduction (UNDRR) Terminology and definitions / elaborations⁵ have provided the basis for an authoritative semantic resource for hazards and disasters, including many marine events. However, there is still no semantic resource (i.e. an ontology or thesaurus) which expresses this terminology with adequate richness to merge into the ODIS knowledge graph, and precise definitions of the various uses of top-level terms such as “hazard”, “exposure”, and “risk” are still elusive. WP12 has begun work to map across several existing assets (D12.1), while nodes within ODIS are sharing data on tsunamis and other relevant phenomena. In pursuit of D11.3, work will begin to express the UNDRR Terminology in the Environment Ontology (ENVO)⁶, which will provide rich links between semantic graphs (the ontology) and knowledge graphs (e.g. the ODIS Graph) to allow greater machine actionability and machine reasoning for AI applications. This will improve actionable links between resources engaged by WP12 and those already federated under ODIS (e.g. for tsunami data⁷).
2. **Cultural Heritage (WP13):** In workshops hosted by WP13, it was determined that the International Image Interoperability Framework (IIIF)⁸ has both the technical foundation and governance structure / mechanisms to provide a sustainable extension of the ODIS

³ Note, however, no governance mechanisms for CDIF have yet been established. Thus WP11 can only provide a technical seed and guidance from the ODIS case study to help initialise CDIF’s mechanisms.

⁴ <https://book.oceaninfohub.org/thematics/README.html>

⁵ <https://www.undrr.org/publication/hazard-definition-and-classification-review-technical-report>

⁶ <https://sites.google.com/site/environmentontology/about-envo>

⁷ https://oceaninfohub.org/results/?search_text=tsunami&page=0 - As of 2023-11-01: retrieving data on 165 documents, 127 Experts, 40 Institutions, 91 Datasets, 71 Training events, 17 Projects, and 25 Spatially qualified records, harvested from ODIS Nodes including the Pacific Data Hub, European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODNet), Indonesian National Oceanic Data Centre, Research Data Australia, and the Dakshin Foundation.

⁸ <https://iiif.io/>

Architecture’s metadata specifications (and hence those of CDIF Core; see Section 3, below). This has applications across the image and video data used in both WP11 and WP13, and offers opportunities to link cultural heritage assets to marine observations, deepening the link between scientific and operational activities at sea and their societal relevance and value. Implementation work on embedding / nesting the IIIF specifications within the CDIF Core “shell” (see Section 3.3.3, below) will be pursued to support WP11-WP13 efforts to implement (meta)data exchanges (in pursuit of D11.3).

3. **Biodiversity (WP09):** ODIS includes the Ocean Biodiversity and Information System (OBIS) as a node, which has a long-standing partnership and persistent (meta)data exchange with GBIF (the primary case study in WP09). As such, the link with biodiversity-oriented programmes in the UN Ocean Decade (as noted in D11.1, 4.1, Point 1a) will naturally deepen WP09-WP11 interoperability. What remains is a validation exercise to ensure that (meta)data from these programmes is detectable via GBIF search and discovery interfaces, indicating that the exchange with OBIS (which will serve as a key hub for the Ocean Decade Actions) includes this incoming (meta)data. Further, through a collaboration with the GEO BON’s BON-in-a-Box initiative⁹, core ODIS technologies and implementation approaches are being deployed in the GEO BON digital ecosystem, seeding new opportunities for cross-domain collaboration across this global network and its mission to deliver biodiversity information to policy makers.
4. **Chemistry (WP03):** Thus far, the progress in WP03 has not been sufficiently integrated into the proceedings of WP11. With the transfer of much of ODIS-Arch into CDIF, new efforts will focus on bridging WP03 and WP11 through CDIF itself. In particular, any representation of IUPAC chemical classifications in JSON-LD with schema.org semantics (e.g. using the ChemicalSubstance¹⁰ or MolecularEntity¹¹ type) has high reuse and interoperability potential.

2. A new, cross-domain interoperability culture based in established global conventions

This section outlines the case for generalising the ODIS Architecture into a core CDIF convention to promote interoperable (meta)data sharing in realistic timeframes and with global coverage. After a brief summary of what ODIS-Arch has achieved, we describe how its domain-neutral specifications and their associated workflows are being transferred into the emerging CDIF commons.

⁹ <https://boninabox.geobon.org/>

¹⁰ <https://schema.org/ChemicalSubstance>

¹¹ <https://schema.org/MolecularEntity>

2.1. Where the ODIS Architecture has brought us

Note: More comprehensive background on ODIS and the ODIS Architecture has been provided in D11.1, Section 1.2. “Initial conditions in WorldFAIR’s Oceanography Work Package”. Here, we highlight the features relevant to the objectives of this deliverable.

The ODIS Architecture (ODIS-Arch) is an interoperability architecture that is revolutionising (meta)data sharing across global ocean stakeholders, and - with support from the Member States in recent assemblies of UNESCO’s Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission (IOC) - has been integrated into the core functioning of the International Oceanographic Data and Information Exchange (IODE). Upon this lightweight architecture, the partners that compose the ODIS Federation¹² (as well as any other stakeholders adopting similar norms¹³) are interoperably sharing, cross-indexing, exploring, and discovering each other’s digital holdings (inclusive of data, metadata, software, and any other digitised entities; see Figure 1). This is a robust foundation for initiatives attempting to secure deeper interoperability across domain-specific or regionally/nationally idiosyncratic scenarios.

Figure 1. A screenshot of the (meta)data themes - generally corresponding to schema.org Types - captured by the initial version of the Ocean InfoHub landing page. Over 100,000 digital assets are being shared by ODIS’s partners, with more coming online each month. Screenshot acquired from <https://oceaninfohub.org/> (accessed 2023-10-31).

Six central components of its success are its:

1. **Technical soundness and leveraging web architecture.** ODIS-Arch is not a new standard or technology - it is a rendition of prevailing web architectural norms¹⁴ that do not require the

¹² Which include multiple European stakeholders, see the ODIS Dashboard for up-to-date listings: <http://dashboard.oceaninfohub.org/>

¹³ I.e. schema.org semantics and JSON-LD serialisation / formatting of shared (meta)data - an approach used by millions of websites across the internet.

¹⁴ <https://book.oceaninfohub.org/content.html>

deployment and (often resource-intensive) maintenance of new APIs or other technologies, which are often beyond the reach of stakeholders. Further, ODIS has recognised that the FAIR Principles can be implemented in many ways, and what is FAIR locally has no guarantee of being FAIR regionally or globally. Partners in the ODIS Federation - through adherence to ODIS-Arch - have a common implementation for (meta)data sharing which is objectively validated through the ODIS dashboard¹⁵ (Figure 2) and its underlying technologies¹⁶.

2. **Clear scope of federation.** The term “federation” is used advisedly in ODIS: its technical foundation is complemented by social conventions that place pluralism within a multilateral framework to build an effective digital ecosystem. Each partner is treated as an independent, digitally sovereign entity with full control over its internal affairs. At the same time, all partners agree to communicate about their holdings via the web architectural patterns described above, with their content (cross-)validated against ODIS-Arch, which they co-develop and co-govern. Scoping the role of the central structures (e.g. IODE and the ODIS Steering Group / Leadership) in the federation is key. These structures moderate the shared power ceded to allow federation, and thus they must have the standing, competencies, and neutrality (via policies and procedural checks and balances) to simultaneously normalise and enhance interactions.
3. **Regional and thematic (i.e. domain) neutrality.** As an initiative operating at global level, engaging with diverse communities and (digital) cultures, special efforts were made to prevent ODIS being captured by regional or thematically/disciplinarily localised norms, or private or public interest groups. Such capture occurs inadvertently in the vast majority of cases, mainly due to a lack of global interoperation as a necessity. This feature was and is particularly important to help reduce digital divides between the Global North and South, as well as across groups with capacity gaps within regions and nations.
4. **Technological neutrality (tool independence).** In a similar vein to point 3, ODIS’s growth, co-development, and potential for sustainability without massive increases in resourcing has been promoted by its technological neutrality. As a system built on standards over tools, the technologies, software, (hyper)local conventions, etc., used by an ODIS node do not affect the core exchange specifications or the operations of any other node. Partners implement the technologies that they find to be the most reasonable in their operational environments, while projecting and consuming (meta)data of known structure and high-level semantics using global web conventions. This feature protects ODIS partners from being “captured” by the conventions or preferences of a dominant region or consortium within the network, which may not serve their local interests.
5. **Open-world perspective.** To make any progress, it is key to accept that the 1) flow of (meta)data to and from global partners will not begin in a harmonised or frictionless manner and 2) partners will (and in many cases are required to) use varied conventions and standards. It is far more important to initialise this flow, to be able to - however imperfectly - share a common digital map of any given datascape. From this intelligence, gradual but

¹⁵ <http://dashboard.oceaninfohub.org/>

¹⁶ <https://book.oceaninfohub.org/validation/index.html>

lasting interoperability can be co-developed through socio-technical alignment and increasingly interlinked activities.

6. **Scalability and sustainability through distributed implementation.** As all ODIS nodes are independent, its scalability is largely arbitrary. Implementations can optimise their usage of ODIS resources by first subsetting content via the metadata discovery layer / index before sourcing larger resources. The entire ODIS graph (not including any linked data resources hosted by partners) is compact and may be efficiently partitioned by region, theme, or other attribute. The distributed nature of ODIS also means that no one implementation is needed for the entire federation to function. If resources such as OIH fail or are no longer supported, the foundational layer of ODIS is unaffected, and can be sustained by any partner or user. Through this feature - and alignment with major search engines - the incentive to continue participating in ODIS even if nodes are lost remains high.

3014339 triples

name	Sitemap Status	Node
benguelacc	✔	Benguela Current Convention (BCC) GeoData Portal
bmdc	✔	Belgian Marine Data Centre (BMDC)
caribbeanma	✔	Caribbean Marine Atlas catalogue
cioos	✔	CIOOS
edmerp	✔	European Directory of Marine Environmental Research Proj
edmo	✔	European Directory of Marine Organisations (EDMO) SeaDa
euroceanorg:	✔	EurOcean Organizations
euroceanpro:	✔	EurOcean Projects
euroceanves:	✔	EurOcean Vessels
emodnet	✔	European Marine Observation and Data Network

type	count
https://schema.org/Person	70,367
https://schema.org/Organization	48,589
https://schema.org/Event	25,934
https://schema.org/CreativeWork	5,761
https://schema.org/Dataset	4,609
https://schema.org/ResearchProject	3,620
https://schema.org/CourseInstance	2,316
https://schema.org/Course	1,618
https://schema.org/Vehicle	115

Figure 2. The ODIS and Ocean InfoHub Dashboard. To validate that the FAIR Principles have been implemented in an interoperable manner across the ODIS Federation, tools such as validators and dashboards have been created. This protects the ODIS Federation from idiosyncratic implementations of the FAIR Principles which may be FAIR locally, but not globally. A similar diagnostic and testing framework is advisable across partners implementing CDIF. Note multiple European assets are federated with their global counterparts (e.g. the European Marine Observation and Data Network; EMODNet), securing their interoperability via global, UN digital architectures.

Upon these components and the guidance in the UN Ocean Decade’s Data and Information Strategy and its emerging Implementation Plan, ODIS is steadily growing across disciplinary and geographical boundaries and is laying a foundation for the fulfilment of the Vision 2030 process. As it does so, a number of current Horizon projects (e.g. Marine Coastal Biodiversity Long-term Observations (MARCO-BOLO)¹⁷ and BiOceans5D¹⁸) are orienting their digital activities and presence such that their outputs are discoverable in ODIS, likely heralding a new regional norm embedded within a global interoperability solution.

2.2. Porting the cross-domain elements of the ODIS Architecture into a CDIF development environment

The co-development of ODIS-Arch has been key to its growth and relevance in the ocean domain: all members of the ODIS Federation are able to transparently extend, update, correct, or otherwise modify the (meta)data interoperability specifications used to secure first-order digital exchange between ODIS partners. This is greatly facilitated by the implementation of ODIS-Arch on GitHub¹⁹ - a widely adopted social coding environment which supports multiple approaches to sharing and maintaining synchronised code bases.

To export the domain-neutral specifications in ODIS-Arch into a collaborative development space aligned to the CDIF mission, the following steps have been taken (illustrated in Figure 3):

1. A GitHub Organization - hosting version-controlled code repositories required to construct CDIF - has been created.²⁰
2. Within that Organization, a repository has been created to host the core interoperability specifications described in this report.²¹
3. A process to transfer the domain-neutral specifications that have been created to support the ODIS-Arch²² and the ODIS Federation has begun, with key specifications (or “patterns”) for the use of schema.org Types such as CreativeWork²³ (of which Dataset²⁴ is a sub-Type) in JSON-LD serialisation prioritised. This will be a continuous process, which will export content as needs arise. **A transfer of 4955 lines of code, contained in 44 files, has been used to**

¹⁷ <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.8208409>

¹⁸ <https://www.biocean5d.org/>

¹⁹ <https://github.com/>

²⁰ <https://github.com/Cross-Domain-Interoperability-Framework>

²¹ <https://github.com/Cross-Domain-Interoperability-Framework/cdif-core>

²² <https://github.com/iodepo/odis-arch/>

²³ <https://schema.org/CreativeWork>

²⁴ <https://schema.org/Dataset>

initialise this process in a pull request^{25,26}, for review by the CDIF collaborative and all members of WorldFAIR who wish to engage.

4. A simultaneous process to expose guidance on using these specifications has also begun, mirroring the ODIS Book publication flow that has supported the ODIS Federation grow and evolve.²⁷

Figure 3. Establishing the CDIF Core interoperability specifications. The generic, domain-neutral components of ODIS Architecture specifications - which have built a foundation to establish and deepen functional, cross-domain interoperability - have been transferred to the CDIF GitHub Organization for broader co-governance and co-design.

Once the pull request associated with these core patterns has been merged into the CDIF Core repository, and these patterns have passed initial validation and quality control by multiple

²⁵

<https://docs.github.com/en/pull-requests/collaborating-with-pull-requests/proposing-changes-to-your-work-with-pull-requests/about-pull-requests>

²⁶ <https://github.com/Cross-Domain-Interoperability-Framework/cdif-core/pull/2>

²⁷ <https://book.oceaninfohub.org/>

WorldFAIR WPs and CDIF working groups, repositories that wish to leverage them can (re)import them and expand upon them if needed (see Section 3.3, below).

3. Establishing the “CDIF Core” specifications

In this section, WP11’s approach to establishing a core set of specifications for cross-domain (meta)data exchange is summarised. This process begins after the transfer of ODIS-Arch specifications into a CDIF Core development environment (Section 2.2), and describes the general process through which all CDIF stakeholders may both (re)use and update the specifications using standard, transparent, and version-controlled development practices.

Why “core”?: These specifications are considered “core” as they offer the most generic level of FAIR (meta)data which domains can use to communicate with one another. Conceptually, domain- or regionally-specific norms and standards radiate away from this generic core, becoming increasingly less cross-domain as they do so.

The CDIF Core specifications and their documentation will be curated and, as needed, modified and expanded upon by the custodians of the CDIF specifications.

3.1. A strong basis in transparent social coding

An essential component in establishing and collaboratively expanding ODIS-Arch was its open and transparent development on GitHub - a platform which integrates social networking technology with normative approaches for the version-controlled development of software and codebases²⁸. Vitally, this was accompanied by clear, open documentation generated as ODIS-Arch grew.

From its beginnings, this approach has protected the core specifications that the ODIS Federation is built upon from being opaque or only available/accessible to a select few (i.e. open but unusable). As such, this has provided a basis for increased digital equity and inclusion of all those who have an internet connection, even if sporadic.

The developer-focused modality of co-developing ODIS-Arch through GitHub is exemplified by the interactions in the *odis-arch* GitHub issue tracker. For example, interoperability was efficiently built in a few, focused exchanges with the South African Marine Information Management System (MIMS)^{29,30}. Exchanges between ODIS and MIMS developers occurred almost entirely over GitHub,

²⁸ Note: GitHub is one of several such solutions. We do not endorse one over the other, but do note that whichever is chosen should have an open character, support portability of all projects they host (should they cease operations), and have robust sustainability plans.

²⁹ <https://data.ocean.gov.za/mims/>

³⁰ A component of the National Oceans and Coasts Information Management System (OCIMS) which manages the Southern African Data Centre for Oceanography (SADCO).

providing a transparent reference for all and reducing the communication and coordination overheads which often impede typical data system alignments³¹.

Such an approach is doubly important in handling the CDIF Core specifications. The processes noted below rely on similar collaborative development environments and transparent, open behaviours. While these are written for the current implementation in GitHub, analogous mechanisms can be found in other systems³².

3.2. Forking and following updates in CDIF Core

Cross-domain efforts wishing to leverage the CDIF Core specifications would (typically) use native GitHub functions to duplicate CDIF Core content, and embed it into their own GitHub Organizations or other organisational structures. The most efficient and normative manner to do so would be to fork³³ the CDIF Core repository into their Organization(s), and create domain-specific variations ***in new files native to their forked repository***. Extensive documentation and guidance on how to create and maintain forks is available, and most contemporary developers are well-versed in their usage, adding to the generalisability and cross-domain applicability of this approach. Alternate approaches, such as the use of submodules³⁴ may sometimes be advisable; however, such a decision to deviate from the more usual repository forking should be carefully considered.

Figure 4. Illustration of the CDIF Core being “forked” into a domain-level GitHub Organization, wherein its content can be integrated into local code development in other repositories, while being anchored to its

³¹ <https://github.com/iodepo/odis-arch/issues/250>

³² For example, GitLab “merge requests” as an analogue to a GitHub pull request:

https://docs.gitlab.com/ee/user/project/merge_requests/

³³ <https://docs.github.com/en/pull-requests/collaborating-with-pull-requests/working-with-forks/about-forks>

³⁴ <https://www.atlassian.com/git/tutorials/git-submodule>

source or “upstream” repository in the CDIF GitHub Organization. This allows any updates to the CDIF Core Repository to be propagated through all forked instances of its content (see below and Figure 5).

Figure 5. Embedding CDIF Core across domains via GitHub forks. Following on from Figure 4, forks of the CDIF Core repository and the specifications within can be maintained by collaborators across domains, and synchronised with any upstream changes (see Figure 6). A similar logic can be followed for regional embeddings. In this standard approach, users / co-developers who wish to embed the CDIF Core into their workflows would either use GitHub’s fork tools, or use generic git operations to add the cdif-core repository into their own workspaces.

Extensive guidance on how to keep all forked versions of a repository up to date (relative to changes in the upstream or source repository; see Figure 6) is available on the GitHub documentation archive³⁵, and common knowledge to most contemporary developers and many researchers across domains. In terms of the CDIF and WorldFAIR missions, such a process will ensure that instances and extensions of CDIF Core are traceable and that its specifications are precisely, unambiguously, and continuously represented across initiatives: a cornerstone of building interoperability.

³⁵ <https://docs.github.com/en/pull-requests/collaborating-with-pull-requests/working-with-forks/syncing-a-fork>

Figure 6. An illustration of CDIF Core content being updated (v1.0 progressing to v2.0 across a time interval $t+1$) and changes being synchronised by a GitHub Organization external to the CDIF Organization using native, standardised, and fully traceable/version-controlled git and GitHub processes.

3.3. Creating, validating, maintaining domain-specific content

3.3.1. Extending CDIF Core

In section 3.2, the approach to fork the CDIF Core repository from the CDIF Organization into one's own development environment was described. For convenience and to support collective awareness of developments (see Section 3.4), domain-level extensions of the CDIF Core may be developed within the forked repositories which have the CDIF Core repository as their source. To do so safely - i.e. without accidentally modifying the CDIF Core specifications themselves - developers are advised to create extensions or variants of CDIF Core specifications in separate files, preferably in a separate branch of their downstream (forked) repository.

As an example, in the ODIS-Arch specifications, a variant of the schema.org type Vehicle was created to support the description of ships and similar vessels³⁶. Note that this specification is still typed as a **Vehicle** to ensure cross-domain recognition and semantic congruence, but additional properties were nested within it to allow more precise / domain-relevant (meta)data exchange by ODIS stakeholders (in line with Section 3.3.2). In this manner, updating/syncing the CDIF Core fork to any

³⁶ <https://github.com/iodepo/odis-in/blob/master/dataGraphs/thematics/vessels/graphs/ship.json>

central updates to the upstream repository will not result in merge conflicts³⁷ and require potentially time consuming refactoring.

As a wider user community for extensions emerges (detected via mechanisms outlined in Section 3.4, for example), the CDIF community can provide concrete bases to motivate higher-level change in the schema.org specification itself. This will require clear demonstration that a wide, global community of users can benefit from and will use new Types and/or properties.

Figure 7. An illustration of domain-specific extensions of CDIF Core maintained within a forked CDIF Core repository in an external GitHub Organization.

3.3.2. Validating extensions

Validating extensions to CDIF Core can leverage the existing validation approach employed by ODIS³⁸ and - in all likelihood - which will also be ported to the CDIF Core community. Generic tools exist for

³⁷

<https://docs.github.com/en/pull-requests/collaborating-with-pull-requests/addressing-merge-conflicts/about-merge-conflicts>

³⁸ <https://book.oceaninfohub.org/validation/index.html>

validating that the usage of JSON-LD and schema.org meets web requirements^{39, 40, 41}, and custom validation approaches can be built and shared as, for example, W3C compliant Shape Constraints Language (SHACL) files⁴². This allows broad freedom to set local norms and criteria, while ensuring that the global basis for interoperability (JSON-LD/schema.org) remains intact. The Dashboard technology developed for the ODIS Federation (see Section 2.1) is open and may be duplicated and extended to continuously and objectively report on the health of new specifications and their application.

Other validation approaches are to be expected across applications and forks of the CDIF Core specifications, however, these must be **based on the schema.org/JSON-LD foundation in CDIF Core as a source of truth** to ensure sustained interoperability.

3.3.3. Nesting domain-specific content in CDIF Core specifications

A key aspect to sustainable and robust extensions of CDIF core is the principle of “nesting” or embedding domain-specific or additional content (e.g. contexts, properties, values, semantics, etc.) within a generic, domain-agnostic “shell”. **The importance of this cannot be overstated:** while it is technically valid to introduce domain-specific contexts⁴³ (or any other contexts not expressly included in the CDIF core source repository) into one of the CDIF core JSON-LD specifications, this effectively obscures them from other users not familiar with their particulars.

While adding entirely new contexts is to be avoided, the current implementation of CDIF core in JSON-LD/schema.org allows the inclusion of additional content from other semantic frameworks , (meta)data conventions, etc. (e.g. Darwin Core; cf. D11.1 for an overview of those noted in the FAIR Implementation Profiles in other WPs). Two approaches are illustrated below.

Firstly, nesting properties outside of the schema.org context is a straightforward process using the schema.org Type `PropertyValue`⁴⁴. Below, this is illustrated by extending the schema context for two variables from the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS) Essential Ocean Variable (EOV) specifications⁴⁵, “Sea State” and “Ocean Surface Stress”.

```
"variableMeasured": [  
  
  {  
    "@type": "PropertyValue",
```

³⁹ <https://validator.schema.org/>

⁴⁰ <http://linter.structured-data.org/>

⁴¹ <https://json-ld.org/playground/>

⁴² <https://www.w3.org/TR/shacl/>

⁴³ <https://www.w3.org/TR/json-ld/#the-context>

⁴⁴ <https://schema.org/PropertyValue>

⁴⁵ <https://www.goosocean.org/eov>

```
"name": "Sea State",
"description": "Sea State is the characterization of wave and
               swell, typically in terms of height, wavelength,
               period, and directional wave energy flux ",
"propertyID": [
  "http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/ENVO_01001374"
],
{
  "@type": "PropertyValue",
  "name": "Ocean Surface Stress",
  "description": "The 2-dimensional horizontal vector Ocean Surface
                 Stress is the rate per unit area at which momentum
                 is transferred from the atmosphere to the ocean.",
  "propertyID": "http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/ENVO_01001844",
  "value": 0.2,
  "unitCode": "http://qudt.org/vocab/unit/N-PER-M2"
}
],
```

Extracted and modified from <https://book.oceaninfohub.org/thematics/variables/index.html>

The human-readable `name` and `description` for each variable is included in their `PropertyValue` specification, but also a `propertyID` with a permanent identifier (PID) to an OWL-encoded ontology that specifies the semantics of each variable with high expressivity. In the second case (“Ocean Surface Stress”), the `value` property of the `PropertyValue` type is used to express the variable’s value, and the `unitCode` property provides a link to a machine-readable representation of the value’s unit in the QUDT standard.

Alternatively, properties that are not included in the domain-agnostic shell can be included in (an array of) `PropertyValue` types as one or more values of an `additionalProperty`⁴⁶.

```
"additionalProperty": {
  "@id": "ID_value_string",
  "@type": "PropertyValue",
  "propertyID": "https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/IMO_number",
  "url": "https://foo.org/linkToPropertyIDPage",
```

⁴⁶ <https://schema.org/additionalProperty>

```
"description": "Any additional properties for the vessel"  
}
```

Extracted and modified from <https://book.oceaninfohub.org/thematics/vessels/index.htm>

Practically, this means all domain-specific content that is redundant with domain-agnostic content should either be:

- a. Replaced with domain-agnostic content; or
- b. Embedded in the domain-agnostic shell, while domain-agnostic counterparts are also instantiated in the record.

This approach is being used to nest, for example, the IIF properties into CDIF Core specifications to promote interoperability with the Cultural Heritage case study (WP13), the Darwin Core specifications native to the biodiversity domain (with bearing on WPs 09 and 10), and any semantic resources developed in the UNDRR context for hazards and disasters (relevant to WP12).

```
"keywords": [  
  "Tuvalu",  
  {  
    "@type": "DefinedTerm",  
    "identifier": "http://purl.org/dc/dcmitype/Image",  
    "inDefinedTermSet": "http://purl.org/dc/terms/DCMIType",  
    "termCode": "Image",  
    "name": "Image"  
  },  
  {  
    "@type": "DefinedTerm",  
    "identifier": "http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/ENVO_01000715",  
    "inDefinedTermSet": "http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/envo",  
    "termCode": "ENVO:01000715",  
    "name": "meteotsunami"  
  }  
]
```

Nesting domain- or regionally-/nationally-specific semantics (e.g. ontology or thesaurus terms and/or their PIDs) should follow a similar logic, leveraging the `schema.org DefinedTerm` type as a value of an appropriate property (e.g. `keyword` or `about`). ODIS has provided some initial

guidance on this approach⁴⁷, which is to be reviewed and expanded upon in the CDIF Core development space.

3.4. Discovering advancements across domains

As a social coding environment, GitHub supports users in tracking how their code has been reused, providing that re-users have employed the standard mechanisms and operating procedures noted above. This is a key functionality for the coordinated growth and community development around the CDIF Core specifications.

Should a CDIF stakeholder wish to examine the “downstream”⁴⁸ work of other co-developers, they can leverage functions in the GitHub API to acquire a list of all forks⁴⁹. An example of this command using the popular command line tool `curl` would resemble:

⁴⁷ <https://book.oceaninfohub.org/thematics/terms/list.html>

⁴⁸ <https://stackoverflow.com/a/2739476>

⁴⁹ <https://docs.github.com/en/rest/repos/forks?apiVersion=2022-11-28#list-forks>

```
curl -L \  
  -H "Accept: application/vnd.github+json" \  
  -H "Authorization: Bearer <YOUR-TOKEN>" \  
  -H "X-GitHub-API-Version: 2022-11-28" \  
  https://api.github.com/repos/OWNER/REPO/forks
```

Where <YOUR-TOKEN> would correspond to the user's access token and OWNER and REPO would be replaced by "Cross-Domain-Interoperability-Framework" and "cdif-core" respectively. A less powerful but more approachable method to those without coding experience is also available via GitHub's online network tracking functionality⁵⁰.

The response would be formatted in rich JSON, and easily parsable to filter (e.g. by date last updated or number of "watchers") and examine work performed by all those maintaining CDIF forks. Such measures can help reduce duplication and create new collaborations between developers who may ordinarily never interact.

3.5. Advancing CDIF Core

Any stakeholder who has forked the CDIF Core repository may - at some juncture - wish to propose modifications to the core specifications themselves. Once again, this can be done in a normative fashion over GitHub, to allow transparency and programmatic tracking/auditing by all. The inclusion of proposed changes requires a formal review process, accompanied by automated validation checks⁵¹, which the emerging CDIF consortium must agree on, perhaps once again drawing inspiration and guidance from ODIS.

Two approaches are expected to be the most common:

- 1. A dedicated fork-and-pull of CDIF Core:** A slight variant of the process described in Section 3.2, a co-developer of CDIF Core would create a new fork of the CDIF Core repository; however, rather than adding any extensions, the developer would modify the upstream assets themselves, validate that their changes are technically sound, and then initiate a pull request to the /Cross-Domain-Interoperability-Framework/cdif-core repository for review.
- 2. A cherry-picked pull request from a domain variant:** If a co-developer wishes to modify upstream assets direct from their repository (described in Section 3.3.1), they would follow

⁵⁰

<https://docs.github.com/en/repositories/viewing-activity-and-data-for-your-repository/understanding-connections-between-repositories>

⁵¹ Likely implemented through GitHub Actions: <https://docs.github.com/en/actions>

the git ‘cherry picking’ process⁵² and create a branch containing only those commits (changes) relevant to their proposed updates of CDIF Core assets. A pull request to merge this branch back to the relevant development branch of the /Cross-Domain-Interoperability-Framework/cdif-core repository would then be initiated (Figure 8).

Figure 8. An illustration of an update to CDIF Core, initiated from a forked repository maintained by a CDIF co-developer. Where only some changes are proposed for reintegration into the *cdif-core* repository, cherry picking (see text) may be used to prevent domain-specific changes impacting upstream repositories.

⁵² <https://learn.microsoft.com/en-us/azure/devops/repos/git/cherry-pick?view=azure-devops&tabs=git-command-line>

4. Policy recommendations

The new specifications and creation of CDIF Core entail several policy considerations, which affect both high-level governance and mid- to low-level technical decisions and operations. While the recommendations below are by no means exhaustive, they seek to demonstrate what policies and policy elements must be in place to effectively deploy and sustain CDIF Core. We offer these in addition to the content in Section 2.1, all of which have served and continue to serve ODIS during its foundation and growth.

4.1. Governance-level recommendations

Stakeholders: Project and programme managers, directorates, high-level decision makers, CTOs

Recommendations:

1. **Technology must closely track intent and behaviour:** Cross-domain interoperability is often fragile, especially during its foundational phases. As such, high-level commitments, strategies, aspirations, and claims *must* be grounded in technological and implementation-level reality. It is relatively trivial to create impressive user interfaces and user experiences in the short-term, but - while superficially impressive - these often actively detract from more lasting and broadly applicable progress.
2. **Governance groups must include a large proportion of individuals fluent⁵³ in the technologies being deployed to meet strategic aims.** It is essential that those developing and maintaining the technology used to accomplish high-level objectives are equal partners in the governance of the missions pursuing them. This measure will help protect initiatives from having decoupled technology and policy, leading to poor governance decisions. This is particularly important when negotiating collaborations and interoperability arrangements with other initiatives: it is imperative that these are not merely performative or sufficient for high-level demonstrations, but deep, flexible, and robust for sustainability.
3. **Include third-party auditing of any interoperability or “FAIR” solutions deployed.** As noted in Section 2, the FAIR Principles can be fulfilled by multiple implementations, and the result may be entirely (individually) FAIR but entirely siloed systems, with incompatible, implementation-level capacities. During mission planning and execution, independent auditors from extra-regional and extra-domain stakeholder groups should be budgeted for and asked to produce periodic evaluation of all interoperability measures taken. Point-by-point responses to their input, detailing changes made or clear justifications for alternatives/non-action should then be published openly.

⁵³ This entails that they actively develop the technologies and/or understand their particulars through direct experience.

4. **Diagnostics and objective validation above all else:** In the realm of cross-domain interoperability, the success function is binary: one is either interoperable or one is not⁵⁴. This must be validated by objective, transparent, and well-documented validation functions that continuously report on the status of interoperability architectures and solutions, and which are designed to verify interoperation across a set of relevant and well-described scenarios. Solutions like the ODIS Dashboard (see Section 2.2) offer an effective way to communicate the technical health of interoperability arrangements across partners to governance teams. The spirit of this recommendation is *clarity*: narrative documents, reports, or other modalities that are typically used to report on interoperability are *insufficiently clear* to express what is actually happening between digital systems. This has multiple undesirable effects, including the promotion of dogmatism over real, measurable, and sustainable interoperability solutions (e.g. dictating regional/thematic standards as the primary means to secure interoperability, when they are non-functional / unfit for purpose and more skilful use of linked open data norms are more appropriate).
5. **Do not allow a domain- or regionally-specific approach to capture a cross-/inter-domain or trans-/inter-regional mission.** In many cases, a group (within a well-resourced domain or region/nation) will create impressive technological solutions that address global challenges. While these have high value, governance groups must resist the urge to port such solutions to their operational environments without careful consideration of whether they have the standing capacity to adapt and sustain such solutions without dependencies on the source. In cases where such local capacities are not in place, there is a strong risk that local systems will be effectively captured by (i.e. strongly dependent on) external systems that are not (primarily) concerned with their priorities and constraints. This often the root of digital colonial dynamics⁵⁵. Any dependent structures or capacities should be implemented in a dedicated interoperability layer of local systems, such that projection of interoperable products can be performed routinely, without compromising internal functionality.
 - a. Special attention should be paid to any data generated through the use of public funds: Public data systems are just as prone to the monopolies and lock-ins that drive cyberbalkanisation⁵⁶ as their commercial counterparts. Most public funders require that (meta)data and information are made openly accessible with highly permissive licences. In practice, however, this is often weakly implemented (often in a “box ticking” manner) and FAIRness is rarely - if ever - verified with the third-parties identified as key stakeholders. Results are often deposited into repositories that may or may not implement the FAIR Principles in any globally meaningful way. The submitted (meta)data itself is also often not well-documented, serialised, or semantically marked-up in a form that would allow efficient (re)use. While preservation is an important step and at least secures the foundation for distributed

⁵⁴ Caveats and imperfect interoperability are expected, but these would be secondary to systems working together (interoperating) in a reasonable fashion such that an end user and/or developer would be able to perform meaningful tasks across these systems without customisations or additional effort / adaptors.

⁵⁵ https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Electronic_colonialism (Retrieved 2023-11-10)

⁵⁶ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Splinternet> (Retrieved 2023-11-23)

data lakes, it is not sufficient for global, cross-domain interoperability. Thus, such (meta)data should be deposited and *professionally assessed*⁵⁷ by repositories which have implemented processes and technologies to make each submission FAIR in a global sense (e.g. oceanographic or ocean-relevant data must have their metadata discoverable via multi-regional systems such as ODIS).

6. **Semantics matter.** It has become increasingly common for technical terminology to become commoditised as “buzzwords” in proposals, outreach/promotional materials, and mid-to-high-level communications. Terms like “data space”, “data lake”, “best practice”, “value chain”, “fit for purpose”, “ontology”, “digital twin”, “indicator”, “essential [ocean, biodiversity, climate] variable”, and even “FAIR” have become almost trivialised, as funders and policy-level stakeholders reward their use, even when the implementation behind the term is poor or far from what the term suggests to those with relevant expertise. Worse still, their absence is often punished (e.g. “the proposal did not commit to creating best practices”) even when it is more honest, realistic, and useful to omit them (e.g. forgoing unverified claims of having a “best practice” in favour of having well-documented and thoroughly tested standard operating procedures). For cross-domain interoperability, loose semantics is fundamentally toxic unless technical terms are used accurately without embellishments⁵⁸.
7. **Decouple engineering from innovation/research.** The reward and incentive structure of research/academia and digital engineering are often at odds. For robust cross-domain interoperability, the closed development and competitive dynamics of seeking citations and “impact” of research publications can often compromise the creation of complete, collaborative, appropriately scoped and marketed, and open-from-inception documentation. This path should be reserved for research conducted on or about engineering artefacts and standards. The artefacts themselves require more formal and open creation and maintenance processes that are led by technical experts, rather than researchers⁵⁹, such as the W3C Process⁶⁰. Scientific peer-review is rarely sufficient or a mark of technical soundness.
8. **Push back against mandates, where they are not fit for (even their own) purpose:** There is increasing pressure on data infrastructures to comply with national, regional, or other community mandates and regulations. In itself, this is neither a good nor a bad development; however, not all mandates are technically or operationally sound. Simply requiring a (meta)data standard does not necessarily improve FAIR implementations or interoperability, just as one cannot mandate that a certain way of building a bridge will work in all scenarios. In close coordination with their technical teams, it is thus recommended

⁵⁷ The professionals noted here are data and information professionals, rather than domain specialists. Most researchers are insufficiently trained to assess whether their (meta)data has aligned to a relevant implementation of the FAIR Principles.

⁵⁸ This is critical and urgent - these terms are used inconsistently by EU projects, infrastructures, and even representatives of the European Commission’s DGs.

⁵⁹ Naturally, cases exist where these roles overlap, however, the role of technical expert must take precedence.

⁶⁰ <https://www.w3.org/2023/Process-20231103/>

that initiatives and organisations clearly and promptly resist top-down mandates *when their diagnostics and objective testing show* they do not serve their intended purposes. This being said, it is also important to note that consumers of (meta)data products may not be able to receive digital assets in the most technically sound or globally aligned manner. See point 3 in the Technical recommendations, below, for recommended solutions.

4.2. Technical recommendations

Stakeholders: data/informatics specialists, digital architects, software developers and team leads, data- or software-focused researchers, (research) data managers.

Recommendations:

- 1. Verify functionality and reject innovation/research-grade products for core capacities.** Foremost, core solutions must work as claimed, and be based on tried-and-tested technologies and methods that have passed well-documented test scenarios. Early on, dashboards (see Section 2) must be created that report on the actual health of a digital system to coordination and management layers of a project. These must verify each claim made at higher levels of the initiative. Research and innovation is of course valuable, but - without rigorous testing in operational contexts by professional software developers - “novel” solutions should not be deployed as part of core infrastructure. It is unfortunately all too often that solutions and technologies are labelled “FAIR” while being based on raw technologies with poor evidence or demonstrations of this fact, especially in terms of FAIRness across *independent* systems. The result is a combination of FAIR silos, territorialism (i.e. insisting that FAIRness within a system/set of standards is superior to that between systems), and cyber-balkanisation. All of these are antithetical to most ideals for the future of data and the internet.
- 2. Qualified user-centrism balanced with implementation-level interests:** The end-user experience is essential to the adoption and skilful use of digital resources (including software, (meta)data, etc). Well-documented approaches to crafting effective user interfaces and experiences (UI/UXs) should be both budgeted for and professionally executed, with focus groups of the intended stakeholder group actively involved in co-development⁶¹ from the earliest stage possible (ideally, pre-proposal). However, the UI/UX layer of interoperable data systems **should not unduly influence the back-end** / foundational digital architectures and decisions/conventions used. These must be well-insulated from one another, allowing the same, robust back-end to serve multiple UI/UXs⁶². Note, however, that UI/UX

⁶¹ The term “co-development” is often used weakly. Here, this entails shared decision-making power of all participants (including user groups). Resolutions on development outcomes and criteria for success should be arrived at through consensus of all parties, and the contributions of stakeholders or other users should not simply be treated as “advice” or “input”.

⁶² By analogy, the core design of a web-page served to a user through a browser should not require or be contingent upon non-standard uses of HTML or CSS, or protocols such as HTTPS.

interoperability is also desirable, and requires its own, focused set of conventions, standards, and aligned FAIR implementations.

3. **Prepare for and implement data space paradigms:** A data space⁶³ is a mature digital ecosystem where each component system or service is capable of integration on demand. Practically, this means that systems should be prepared to convert their internal holdings into forms governed by standards that other systems can understand and ingest. This also means that systems should have the ability to ingest and integrate data from other systems, not by writing a potentially endless suite of domain-to-domain converters, but by harvesting content in the common, professionalised forms (see point 7, in this section) accepted in the data space. In essence, the ODIS and now CDIF Core approach embodies this philosophy, with the systems in ODIS Federation converting their (meta)data into JSON-LD/schema.org for common interoperability. This design logic will inevitably become a central feature of cross-domain interoperability, and is supported by the emerging CDIF Principles⁶⁴ of atomicity and a stable externalisation layer.
4. **Non-normative version control and social coding behaviour is not to be supported.** Software and technical development is not an unsolved or novel space, even if its subjects are novel or research-oriented. Hence, there are standard ways of handling digital assets (e.g. well-documented GitHub processes, outlined above) and version controlling outputs and progress. Unfortunately, these skills are still not normative in research, resulting in poor referencing and tracking of development (e.g. even data journals allowing authors to reference GitHub repositories rather than tagged releases of said repositories archived in a long-term archive). In the spirit of reproducibility and reusability (cornerstones of scientific research and FAIR, respectively), undisciplined use of systems that are essential to tracking the provenance of digital assets cannot be endorsed and should be actively discouraged.
5. **Interoperability logic should be in the (meta)data itself, rather than in any application-layer solutions.** The proliferation of digital tools, services, virtual research environments, software, digital twins, and other applications is exponential. While exciting, these advancements must be carefully managed to support - and not impede - cross-domain interoperability. Briefly: if interoperability depends on a certain tool or system being in place and maintained, rather than agreements on what is exchanged between applications and systems, then immense risks have been created. The application has become a dependency, and likely a bottleneck and a silo. Agreements should be made on the input/output streams

⁶³ As noted in Section 4.1, point 6 - the term “data space” has unfortunately become semantically confounded. However, the general notion of allowing diverse partners to interoperate by converting and exchanging their local digital assets via standards under acceptable co-governance regimes seems to be a stable element. For background, see (all links verified 2023-11-29):

- <https://design-principles-for-data-spaces.org/>
- https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-93975-5_2
- <https://internationaldataspaces.org/why/data-spaces/>

⁶⁴

<https://github.com/Cross-Domain-Interoperability-Framework/principles/tree/3c6691bd2e3a05a60e35eba08cfc89c0f8330a60>

between such applications, so developers need not know any of the intra-application conventions, but only how to push and pull data between them. APIs and passive structured-data-on-the-web approaches are based on such logic; however, simply adopting these is no guarantee that the (meta)data exchanged is interoperable (i.e. shares conventions).

6. **Five-star linked open data⁶⁵ is still the aim, but is often obfuscated.** The vision of five-star linked open data has still not been fulfilled. This is not due to any significant technical impediment, but a general lack of will to co-implement interoperable systems. Rationalisations that generally amount to “we do it better” or “we don’t control this, so we’ll use our local solution” are common. As ODIS has shown, building consensus around broadly adopted standards and patterns, and a co-development environment under light but stabilising governance / oversight can build multi-domain federations that do - indeed - have a firm foothold in building interoperability conventions based on LOD.
7. **Transition domain-specific formats to those that are more generic and performance-focused.** Many (sub)domains have developed - often through grassroots initiatives and consortia - their own formats and serialisations. These often require bespoke software to process, creating another class of silo and impediment to cross-domain interoperability. To support broader interoperability and performance, these should be converted to open, generic formats that have been optimised to for common programming languages and compute infrastructures (e.g. Apache parquet⁶⁶ or Zarr⁶⁷).
8. **Generic content should pass validation, even after domain-specific content is stripped away.** Assuming that (meta)data has been encoded in a robust format, which is not corrupted by modular/principled removal of components, the removal of all domain-specific content (e.g. any nested content as outlined in Section 3.3.3) should result in a valid file that has enough generically qualified (meta)data to make basic sense of its (intended) content. This will allow discovery and basic operations to be performed on files shared between domains with no understanding of one another’s internal conventions.
9. **Decouple metadata and data records.** Several formats bundle metadata and data in one file or record⁶⁸. While there is nothing inherently wrong with this approach, it can compromise FAIR sub-principle A2⁶⁹ and independent files hosting metadata in a generic format (e.g. JSON-LD), and linked to the data via LOD approaches, should be created and maintained.
10. **Keep all interoperability standards up-to-date.** Automated notifications of any new releases or changes to any standards used in developing cross-domain interoperability norms should be in place to facilitate updates of these norms. Where issues emerge, resolutions and adaptations should be propagated to all adopters/users (see Section 3.2 for one such

⁶⁵ <https://5stardata.info/en/>

⁶⁶ <https://parquet.apache.org/>; see esp. <https://parquet.apache.org/docs/overview/motivation/>

⁶⁷ <https://zarr.dev/>

⁶⁸ E.g. the popular Network Common Data Form (NetCDF), commonly used in oceanography: <https://www.unidata.ucar.edu/software/netcdf/>

⁶⁹ <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/a2-metadata-accessible-even-data-no-longer-available/>

model). This is generally common practice, but also frequently overlooked. In cross-domain settings, the importance of maintaining synchronised standards is heightened.

11. **Semantics matter.** The semantic resources used to create and maintain cross-domain interoperability must be of high quality and (as noted above) operational/engineering-grade and well maintained, rather than research or innovation products. As ODIS and many others have shown with the schema.org vocabulary, interoperability is possible with relatively loose, low expressivity⁷⁰, but well-scoped semantic resources, which can be extended for precision (as shown in Section 3.3.3). ***The expressivity of any semantic resource chosen must match the competencies demanded of them:*** in some cases, a controlled vocabulary without term definitions is sufficient (or even preferable, when precise definitions are not agreed upon globally); in others, one needs a SKOS-encoded thesaurus or an OWL-encoded⁷¹ ontology with formal logic. Any solution chosen must be technically sound, appropriate to the entities being described, and subject to validation checks appropriate to its scope. Where semantic resources describing common phenomena are in play, developers should seek and import authoritative cross-walks, encoded in a machine-actionable format such as Simple Standard for Sharing Ontological Mappings (SSSOM)⁷². Where no such authoritative mappings exist, developers should request these are produced by a suitable mix of domain and semantic technology experts (for example, see Duerr et al. 2023⁷³) and the leads of any resources mapped informed of any outputs, and requested to review and endorse them.

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⁷⁰ That is, low expressivity as compared to fully fledged semantic solutions such as formal ontologies.

⁷¹ Note, however, the encoding itself is not an indication of semantic expressivity or quality. SKOS and OWL are simply formats. They do not inform one of content quality. As an analogy, just because a text is encoded in DOCX, does not tell you if it is worth reading.

⁷² <https://mapping-commons.github.io/sssom/about/>

⁷³ <https://doi.org/10.31223/X5C966>